

COMPARISON OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS IN PHYSICS

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Abstract: *We consider theoretical and practical physics. We define them. We will find out what is included in theoretical and practical physics.*

Keywords: *theoretical physics, methodology, practical physics, practical content*

Theoretical physics is a branch of physics in which the creation of theoretical models of phenomena and their comparison with reality is used as the main way of knowing nature. In this formulation, theoretical physics is an independent method of studying nature, although its content is naturally formed taking into account the results of experiments and observations of nature.

The methodology of theoretical physics consists in the identification of key physical concepts and the formulation in mathematical language of the laws of nature linking these concepts; explanation of the observed phenomena of nature on the basis of formulated laws of nature; prediction of new natural phenomena that can be detected.

The product of theoretical physics is physical theories. Since theoretical physics works precisely with mathematical models, the mathematical consistency of a completed physical theory is an extremely important requirement. The second mandatory property that distinguishes theoretical physics from mathematics is the ability to obtain predictions within the theory for the behavior of nature under certain conditions (that is, predictions for experiments) and, in cases where the result of the experiment is already known, to agree with the experiment.

The above allows us to outline the general structure of the physical theory. It should contain:

a description of the range of phenomena for which a mathematical model is being constructed,

axioms defining a mathematical model,

axioms comparing observables, physical objects,

direct consequences of mathematical axioms and their equivalents in the real world, which are interpreted as predictions of the theory.

One of the effective means of forming students' theoretical knowledge and developing their practical skills are physical tasks with practical content.

The scientific and methodological literature does not provide a definition of a physical problem with practical content. By a physical task with practical content, we will understand a task aimed at identifying the physical essence of objects of nature, production and everyday life with which a person interacts in the course of his practical activity.

Determining the place of tasks with practical content in the process of teaching physics necessitates the allocation of functions that they perform in the educational process.

Solving problems with practical content is of great educational importance, since it contributes to the formation of personal qualities in schoolchildren, such as will, perseverance, initiative, ingenuity, perseverance, independence, etc.;

The motivating function is that tasks with practical content are a means of activating attention and developing cognitive interest in the material being studied.

Solving practical problems of a problematic nature contributes to the emergence of a student's personal interest in getting an answer to the question of the problem, the conclusion of students' cognitive search.

Solving problems with practical content creates conditions for predicting the results and possible consequences of practical human interaction with objects.

Ensures the formation of students' readiness to perform practical activities. In the process of solving problems with practical content, the unity of tasks in creative and practical aspects is revealed (the acquired knowledge and skills are the basis for the formation of personal life experience of students).

Tasks with practical content make it possible to control knowledge and develop practical skills on their basis.

The motivational function of tasks with practical content is manifested in the fact that their solution contributes to students' awareness of the airiness of the role of physical knowledge and practical skills in human life and the need to master knowledge and skills for the qualitative performance of any activity.

When selecting such tasks, it is necessary to follow certain rules:

- The possibility of using each task for the simultaneous formation of theoretical knowledge and practical skills on its basis; its essence lies in the fact that tasks with practical content act in the process of teaching physics as a means of forming theoretical knowledge and a means of developing students' practical skills.

- Operational use of the results of solving problems in the process of human life; training is closely related to human life and is not carried out outside of it. In the process of learning, there is a constant orientation of the studied material to its use in human life.

- The potential possibility of using the results of solving problems in further practical activities; the implementation of this rule involves the use of tasks with practical content to form students' readiness to apply the acquired knowledge and skills in further practical activities.

- The availability of task material is too much for a given age and level of preparedness, students' learning material causes them to tire quickly, reducing the motivational mood for exercises. As a consequence, the working capacity of schoolchildren decreases, but excessive simplification of the task material leads to a drop in the interests of schoolchildren to study, artificially inhibits the development of students.

- Differentiation and individualization.

- The most important means of teaching is visibility. The creation of a set of tasks taking into account the principle of visibility will allow to develop the attention of students, increase the effectiveness of learning by involving the senses to the perception and processing of educational material. You can use various means of visualization: natural technical objects, existing devices and models, homemade devices and installations, household appliances and accessories, tables and codograms of technical objects, etc.

Conclusion: As we see, we need theoretical knowledge to understand nature, create theoretical models and compare them with reality. And we need practical knowledge in order to solve problems. These two are of great importance and they complement each other.

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